

HERCCULES
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Preliminary CFD-based simulations to support oxyfuel calciner design

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D2.1 Preliminary CFD-based simulations to support oxyfuel calciner design

Deliverable title Work Package Lead beneficiary Due Date Actual delivery date Dissemination level Abstract	Preliminary CFD-based simulations to support oxyfuel calciner design WP2 LUT 31/10/2023 31/10/2023 Public This report presents a summary of the used modeling tools and the work performed on the preliminary development of the oxyfuel pre-calciner concept for the cement industry. Different modeling approaches are taken in series and parallel to define the concept and additional details are investigated at each phase to evaluate the preliminary pre-calciner design. 0D process modeling is the initial step, followed by 1D and 3D reactor modeling and CFD simulations of the bottom part of the reactor.
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1 INTRODUCTION

This report describes the work performed in the HERCCULES project under work package 2 for modeling the initial concept of 1.5 MW_{th} oxy-fuel pre-calciner to be utilized in TITAN cement plant to enable CO₂ capture while processing 750,000 tons of clinker annually.

The work was performed as follows. Initial 0D process modeling was performed by LEAP and POLIMI to find the required reactor parameters for an oxy-fuel pre-calciner operating in pneumatic transport mode to reach the desired conditions. This information was utilized by LUT in 1D modeling to obtain the required calciner height and this information was combined with 0D process model results to enable 3D process modeling of the initial pre-calciner concept as well as a detailed computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation of the raw meal, fuel and oxygen feeding to the pre-calciner.

2 METHODS

2.1 0D model

The main objective of the 0D modeling is to find a suitable concept and initial design for the pre-calciner for further, more detailed investigations. Aspen Plus was used for solving the necessary mass and energy balance equations. For the solid compounds, the pure components NIST database is available in Aspen Plus and the NASA polynomial expressions for thermodynamic properties have been selected. The thermodynamic property method based on the Peng-Robinson equation of state has been adopted for modeling the gas phase compounds.

Figure 1 shows the block diagram of the system used to evaluate mass and energy balances. The oxy-calciner has inputs of recirculated CO₂-rich gas (stream 7), oxygen (4), fuel (3), and raw meal (0), and outputs of CO₂-rich gas (6) and calcined material (5).

Figure 1. 0D model domain and input and output streams.

The design was performed for a 1.5 MW_{th} calciner with a targeted calcination degree of 90%, which is defined as the molar ratio of calcium oxide to the total calcium in the sorbent. The oxygen flow rate was set to have a content of oxygen equal to 3.5%-vol (on dry-basis) in the oxy-calciner off-gas. The targeted outlet temperature for the calciner was set at 920 °C to ensure high-level of calcination with high partial pressure levels of CO₂ (Silcox et al. 1989) and the circulation gas temperature of 400 °C was applied. Pneumatic transport at gas velocities over 15 m/s was considered as a design parameter as it is typically adopted for entrained flow reactors in the cement industry (Spinelli et al. 2018).

Figure 2 presents the flowchart for the 0D modeling for the oxy-calciner. The target value of the oxygen concentration in the oxidizing stream entering the calciner burner (stream 9 in Figure 1) is 50%-vol. This was controlled by varying the flue gas circulation rate back to the calciner. The O₂ concentration in the calciner oxidizing gas is related to the thermal efficiency of the oxy-combustion process. The higher the O₂ content, the lower the flue gas recirculation rate and thus the fuel consumption. On the other hand, the circulation of the CO₂-rich flue gases back to the calciner enables reaching the required gas velocities (with a reasonable reactor diameter) and solid-to-gas -ratios in the reactor and controlling the maximum temperature in the combustion section. The value of 50% for the O₂ concentration at the calciner inlet represents efficient reactor operating conditions.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the oxy-calciner in 0D process modeling.

2.2 1D model

The main objective of the 1D modeling is to find the height required for the reactor to achieve a sufficiently high degree of calcination for the process to work as intended. The 1D model was developed during the HORIZON2020 funded CLEANER project for modeling of entrained flow reactor utilized in calcium looping processes. It is based on the 1D model developed by Ylätaalo (2014) for the calcium looping process with dual fluidized bed reactors. The model utilizes a finite volume method for transient simulation of mass, species, and energy balances in pneumatic transport conditions, with the assumptions of slip velocity equaling the terminal velocity of the particles, and a constant vertical density profile and solid flux with the solid concentration of 2%-vol. The overall model frame is illustrated in Figure 3 for a calcium looping system. More details of the 1D model are presented by Sakas (2019).

Figure 3. 1D model framework illustration.

In the 1D model, the combustion of solid fuel is not currently considered, thus the combustion of solid fuels was handled by inserting a corresponding mixture of flue gas and thermal energy into the reactor as an input, while gas combustion is modeled within the model frame.

2.3 3D model

The 3D model was created to simulate combustion in a circulating fluidized bed (CFB) furnace. The model was further developed to allow the modeling of various fluidized bed reactors and processes, as well as pneumatic transport reactors. In the model, the reactor is modeled three-dimensionally

with the control volume method, and various balance equations are solved in a steady-state condition. The model considers various phenomena: flow dynamics of gas and solids in an Eulerian reference frame, reactions, comminution, and heat transfer. The particle size distribution and the comminution of solids are simulated by dividing solid materials into multiple particle size groups or fractions. The illustration of the model frame is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The framework of the 3D model. (Myöhänen and Hyppänen 2011)

The 3D model developed by LUT was employed to investigate the oxygen-fired calciner in more detail. In the reactor systems involving calcium-containing sorbents, the continuity of the total sorbent fractions is defined as follows:

$$\oint_A \varepsilon_{sorb,i} \rho_{sorb} \mathbf{v}_{sorb,i} \cdot d\mathbf{A} = \int_V \phi'''_{sorb,i} dV + \int_V R'''_{sorb,i} dV - \int_V \sum_{j,j \neq i} k_{C,sorb,ij} \varepsilon_{sorb,i} \rho_{sorb} dV + \int_V \sum_{j,j \neq i} k_{C,sorb,ji} \varepsilon_{sorb,j} \rho_{sorb} dV \quad 2.1$$

This includes terms for convection, sources and sinks, reactions, and comminution between the size fractions. The net velocity field of the sorbent is defined separately for each particle size fraction. A flow potential is defined for each size fraction:

$$\varepsilon_{sorb,i} \rho_{sorb} \mathbf{v}_{sorb,i} = \nabla P_{f,s,sorb,i} \quad 2.2$$

The potential difference across the furnace outlet faces is set based on the determined constant outlet velocity for total solids. Combining the above equations, the potential fields $P_{fs,sorb,i}$ can be solved, after which the sorbent velocity for each size fraction is defined from Equation 2.2.

The modeled sorbent reactions are:

- | | |
|------------------------------|--|
| 1) Calcination | $\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$ |
| 2) Carbonation | $\text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CaCO}_3$ |
| 3) Indirect sulfation | $\text{CaO} + \text{SO}_2 + 0.5 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CaSO}_4$ |
| 4) Direct sulfation | $\text{CaCO}_3 + \text{SO}_2 + 0.5 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CaSO}_4 + \text{CO}_2$ |
| 5) Desulfation | $\text{CaSO}_4 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{SO}_2 + 0.5 \text{O}_2$ |
| 6) Belite formation from CaO | $\text{CaO} + 0.5 \text{SiO}_2 \rightarrow 0.5 \text{Ca}_2\text{SiO}_4$ |

The silica (SiO_2) is not explicitly simulated: the model assumes that the amount of SiO_2 is always sufficient and the belite formation is not limited by the concentration of SiO_2 . For that reason, the CaO bound to belite is denoted in the model by a species named CaO_B. In the model, this CaO_B is no longer able to participate in other sorbent reactions.

Continuity equations are defined for each particle size fraction i and for each reacting sorbent species r (CaCO_3 , CaO , CaSO_4 , CaO_B):

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \oint_A w_{r,i} \varepsilon_{sorb,i} \rho_{sorb} \mathbf{v}_{sorb,i} \cdot d\mathbf{A} - \oint_A \varepsilon_{sorb,i} \rho_{sorb} D_{sorb,i} \nabla w_{r,i} \cdot d\mathbf{A} \\
 & = \int_V \phi_{r,i}''' dV + \int_V R_{r,i}''' dV \\
 & - \int_V \sum_{j,j \neq i} w_{r,i} k_{C,sorb,ij} \varepsilon_{sorb,i} \rho_{sorb} dV + \int_V \sum_{j,j \neq i} w_{r,j} k_{C,sorb,ji} \varepsilon_{sorb,j} \rho_{sorb} dV
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

Equation 2.3 includes the following terms: 1) convection, 2) dispersion, 3) sources, 4) reactions, 5) comminution to other size fractions, and 6) comminution from other size fractions. The term $w_{r,i}$ is a fraction specific weight fraction of species r .

The dispersion constants are defined separately for each furnace zone, each size fraction, and vertical and horizontal directions, but they are assumed to be the same for all sorbent species.

The different sorbent reactions are controlled by fraction-specific reaction rate expressions for each reaction $reac$ and reacting sorbent species r :

$$R_{reac,i}''' = k_{reac,i} \varepsilon_{r,i} \rho_r \tag{2.4}$$

Table 1 presents the relation between different species (r) and reactions ($reac$) and the sign of reaction rate constants (k_{reac}). A negative rate constant indicates the reacting (i.e. consuming) species (e.g. CaCO_3 in calcination).

Table 1. Calculation parameters for sorbent reactions.

Reaction (<i>reac</i>)	Abbr.	Equation	Species (<i>r</i>)			
			CaCO ₃	CaO	CaSO ₄	CaO_B
Calcination	Calc	CaCO ₃ →CaO+CO ₂	-k _{calc}	+k _{calc}		
Carbonation	Carb	CaO+CO ₂ →CaCO ₃	+k _{carb}	-k _{carb}		
Sulfation	Sulf	CaO+SO ₂ +½O ₂ →CaSO ₄		-k _{sulf}	+k _{sulf}	
Direct sulfation	Dirs	CaCO ₃ +SO ₂ +½O ₂ →CaSO ₄ +CO ₂	-k _{dirs}		+k _{dirs}	
Desulfation	Desu	CaSO ₄ →CaO+SO ₂ +½O ₂		+k _{desu}	-k _{desu}	
Belite formation from CaO	Beli	CaO + ½SiO ₂ →½Ca ₂ SiO ₄				-k _{beli}

The species-specific reaction term $R''_{r,i}$ in the continuity equation combines the different reactions for each species, for example, the reactions defined for CaSO₄:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R''_{CaSO_4,i} = & +k_{sulf,i} \varepsilon_{CaO,i} \rho_{CaO} \frac{M_{CaSO_4}}{M_{CaO}} \\
 & + k_{dirs,i} \varepsilon_{CaCO_3,i} \rho_{CaCO_3} \frac{M_{CaSO_4}}{M_{CaCO_3}} \\
 & - k_{desu,i} \varepsilon_{CaSO_4,i} \rho_{CaSO_4}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

The reaction rate constants are determined by the following correlations.

Calcination (Khinast et al., 1996):

$$k_{calc} = c_{calc} 870 893 \exp\left(\frac{-133 000}{RT}\right) \exp\left(-1.38 \frac{p_{CO_2}}{p_{eq}}\right) (1 - X_{CaO})^{(2/3)} \tag{2.6}$$

Carbonation (Graca et al. 2008):

$$k_{carb} = c_{carb} 4.0 \exp\left(\frac{-25 000}{RT}\right) (p_{CO_2} - p_{eq}) (X_{max} - X_{CaCO_3})^{(2/3)} \tag{2.7}$$

Equilibrium pressure (Silcox et al. 1989):

$$p_{eq} = 4.137 \cdot 10^7 \exp\left(\frac{-20 474}{T}\right) \tag{2.8}$$

Sulfation (Myöhänen et al. 2011):

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_{sulf,i} = & c_{sulf} 20.0 \exp\left(\frac{-2400}{T}\right) \exp(-5.0 X_{CaSO_4,i}) C_{SO_2} C_{O_2} M_{CaO} \\
 & \max(C_{O_2}) = 0.5 \text{ mol/m}^3
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

Direct sulfation (Myöhänen et al. 2011):

$$k_{dirs,i} = c_{dirs} 3.0 \exp\left(\frac{-3031}{T}\right) C_{SO_2}^{0.9} C_{CO_2}^{-0.75} C_{O_2}^{0.001} M_{CaCO_3} \tag{2.10}$$

Desulfation (Myöhänen et al. 2011):

$$k_{desu,i} = c_{desu} 0.5 \exp\left(\frac{-10\,000}{T}\right) C_{CO} M_{CaSO_4} \quad 2.11$$

Belite formation (derived from Jander and Hoffmann 1934):

$$k_{beli} = c_{beli} \frac{\frac{3}{2} 4.35E10 \exp\left(\frac{-336\,000}{RT}\right) (1 - X_{CaO_B})^{2/3}}{1 - (1 - X_{CaO_B})^{1/3}} \quad 2.12$$

At the beginning of belite formation, the mole fraction of belite $X_{CaO_B} = 0$ which would lead to divide-by-zero in Equation 2.12. This is handled by using the original conversion correlation by Jander and Hoffmann (1934) to determine the conversion at 5 s time:

$$X_{CaO_B,5s} = 1 - \left[1 - (5.0 k_{beli})^{1/2}\right]^3 \quad 2.13$$

When the belite fraction is smaller than the above limit, the reaction rate is constant:

$$k_{beli}(X_{CaO_B} < X_{CaO_B,5s}) = \frac{X_{CaO_B,5s}}{5\,s} \quad 2.14$$

The different reaction coefficients c_{calc} , c_{carb} , c_{sulf} , c_{dirc} , and c_{beli} were set to unity. These can be later applied to calibrate the reaction rates based on experimental data. The other parameters in the equations include molar fractions of different species (X), molar concentrations in gas (C , mol/m³), molar weights (M , kg/mol), and temperature (T , K). The maximum carbonation molar fraction X_{max} was set to 0.4. However, in this calculation, the reactor temperature was high enough to prevent carbonation, thus the carbonation reaction parameters did not affect the results.

The other submodels related to combustion, fluid dynamics, and heat transfer have been presented by Myöhänen and Hyppänen (2011) and the application of the 3D model to a calcium looping process has been presented by Parkkinen et al. (2017).

2.4 CFD model

Ansys Fluent was used as the CFD software for the modeling. Based on the initial dimensions obtained from the 0D and 1D analyses, a tube reactor model was constructed with a generic splash box type of mixing chamber at the bottom of the reactor. Splash boxes are commonly used in the cement industry for feeding solids to reactors, and in this study, a two-sided splash box was used to allow for a more uniform distribution of solids in the reactor. The bottom of the reactor is illustrated in Figure 5 with raw meal inlets located at the top, fuel feeding from the sides, an inlet gas stream from the bottom, and an outlet (continuation of the tube reactor) at the top. The same mixing chamber design is also used with the 3D process model.

Transient Lagrangian-Eulerian simulations were performed with an estimated particle size distribution for the raw meal, with the gas phase modeled as an Eulerian phase and the particles as a Lagrangian phase using the dense discrete phase model. Species transport, chemical reactions, and heat transfer were considered due to their effects on the flow hydrodynamics to evaluate the mixing of particles. The inputs were selected based on inputs and guiding principles of 0D and 1D models.

Figure 5. Mixing chamber design in the CFD and 3D simulations.

2.5 Inputs for different models

The different models in this work use the same or similar inputs, thus they are collectively presented in this section. Table 2 presents the raw meal composition provided by TITAN for 0D modeling. Fuel data are presented in Table 3 for the biochar, Table 4 for the solid recovered fuel, and Table 5 for the biogas. As the objective is to model oxy-combustion, the input oxygen content is taken as approximately 50%-vol.

Table 2. Chemical composition of raw meal.

CaCO ₃ (%-wt)	SiO ₂ (%-wt)	Al ₂ O ₃ (%-wt)	Fe ₂ O ₃ (%-wt)	MgCO ₃ (%-wt)	H ₂ O (%-wt)
75.56	13.54	3.04	2.98	4.37	0.51

Table 3. Proximate and ultimate analysis of the biochar.

Proximate analysis (%-wt)				Ultimate analysis (%-wt)					LHV (MJ/kg)
Moisture	Ash	VM	FC	C	H	N	S	O	
0.69	6.0	12.37	80.94	88.41	3.90	2.15	4.79	0.74	33.07

Table 4. Proximate and ultimate analysis of the solid recovered fuel (SRF).

Proximate analysis (%-wt)				Ultimate analysis (%-wt)					LHV (MJ/kg)
Moisture	Ash	VM	FC	C	H	N	S	O	
12.00	10.68	76.86	12.46	70.61	10.82	0.31	0.19	18.07	21.86

Table 5. Composition and ultimate analysis of the biogas.

Gas composition (%-mol)			Ultimate analysis (%-wt)					LHV (kJ/kg)
CH ₄	C ₃ H ₈	N ₂	C	H	N	S	O	
90.0	6.0	4.0	71.2	22.6	6.2	0	0	46.4

Input for the fresh raw meal for the 0D model is presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Fresh raw meal input data.

Stream	Temperature	Mass flow rate
	°C	kg/h
0: Fresh raw meal	60.0	2600

The inlet gas streams and solid circulation stream are calculated to meet the criteria presented in section 2.1, thus they are presented together with the results.

Based on experiences from the CLEANKER project, it is estimated that air leakage will occur in the process, with the total leakage taken as 400 Nm³/h in the 0D model. In the 1D model, 100 Nm³/h is assumed to occur in the reactor, with the air leakage divided over the reactor with 6 m intervals to represent possible leaks from the seams of the reactor.

3 RESULTS

3.1 0D model

The modeled solid stream outputs are presented in Table 7 and gas stream inputs and outputs are presented in Table 8. As described earlier, the thermal power of the calciner was set to 1.5 MW and calcination degree to 90%.

Table 7. Solid stream outputs for biochar, biogas, and SRF+biochar.

Stream	Temperature	Mass Flows	Mass composition							
	°C		kg/h	CaO	CaCO ₃	CaSO ₄	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgCO ₃
BIOCHAR										
2	478.3	2807.3	9.5%	63.1%	0.0%	20.4%	3.4%	1.9%	0.0%	1.7%
5	15.0	382.0	54.9%	8.4%	0.0%	27.5%	4.5%	2.5%	0.0%	2.3%
7	386.1	66.5	9.5%	63.1%	0.0%	20.4%	3.4%	1.9%	0.0%	1.7%
BIOGAS										
2	469.1	2815.0	9.4%	63.3%	0.0%	20.3%	3.4%	1.9%	0.0%	1.7%
5	15.0	398.4	55.2%	8.4%	0.0%	27.0%	4.5%	2.5%	0.0%	2.3%
7	385.6	39.2	9.4%	63.3%	0.0%	20.3%	3.4%	1.9%	0.0%	1.7%
SRF + BIOCHAR										
2	510.7	2284.6	9.5%	63.1%	0.0%	20.5%	3.4%	1.9%	0.0%	1.7%
5	920.1	1329.0	54.5%	8.3%	0.0%	28.0%	4.5%	2.4%	0.0%	2.3%
7	385.5	52.5	9.5%	63.1%	0.0%	20.5%	3.4%	1.9%	0.0%	1.7%

Table 8. Gas stream iterated inputs and outputs for biochar, biogas and SRF+biochar.

Stream	Temperature	Mass Flows	Molar composition				
	°C		kg/h	CO ₂	H ₂ O	N ₂	O ₂
BIOCHAR							
4	15.0	382.0	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%
7	386.1	494.8	57.6%	7.6%	28.7%	5.7%	0.5%
8	386.1	1827.2	57.6%	7.6%	28.7%	5.7%	0.5%
9	248.7	876.8	30.5%	4.0%	15.2%	50.1%	0.2%
BIOGAS							
4	15.0	398.4	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%
7	385.6	258.4	43.9%	25.0%	26.1%	5.0%	0.0%
8	385.6	1803.9	43.9%	25.0%	26.1%	5.0%	0.0%
9	193.3	656.8	17.0%	9.7%	10.1%	63.2%	0.0%
SRF + BIOCHAR							
4	15.0	376.7	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%
7	385.5	444.2	47.2%	19.4%	28.1%	5.2%	0.1%
8	385.5	1704.3	47.2%	19.4%	28.1%	5.2%	0.1%
9	234	820.9	25.6%	10.5%	15.2%	48.7%	0.0%

Table 9 presents 0D simulation results with different fuels. With the given gas streams and predefined gas velocity, the preliminary diameter of the riser was taken as 325 mm, which is used as an input parameter in other models. Also, these calculated results are used as input values in subsequent simulations.

Table 9. 0D simulation results (for the numbering of the streams, refer to Figure 1).

Result (stream number in parenthesis)		Biochar	Biogas	SRF+Biochar
Fresh raw meal (0)	kg/h	2572	2605	2143
Total fuel to calciner (3)	kg/h	175	116	200
Oxygen input (4)	kg/h	389	399	377
Vol. flow rate at calciner outlet	Nm ³ /h	1194	1172	1190
O ₂ at calciner inlet	%-vol, wet-basis	50.01	64.03	48.70
CO ₂ at calciner outlet	%-vol, wet-basis	30.41	16.85	70.38
Gas velocity at calciner outlet	m/s	17.7	17.4	17.6
O ₂ at calciner outlet	%-vol, dry-basis	3.50	3.50	3.50
CO ₂ at calciner outlet	%-vol, dry-basis	73.38	71.71	70.38
CO ₂ -rich gas to CPU (8)	Nm ³ /h	1133	1248	1128
CO ₂ -rich gas recirculated to calciner (7)	Nm ³ /h	307	170	294
Solid-to-gas -ratio at calciner inlet section	kg/Nm ³	3.87	3.96	2.97
Solid-to-gas -ratio at calciner outlet section	kg/Nm ³	1.74	1.75	1.49
Solid-to-gas -ratio at preheater riser	kg/Nm ³	2.25	2.31	1.92
Total false air to CO ₂ -rich gas (6) ratio	%-vol, dry-basis	29.9	30.3	30.3
CO ₂ at CO ₂ -rich gas to CPU (8)	%-vol, dry-basis	62.83	59.09	58.59
O ₂ at CO ₂ -rich gas to CPU (8)	%-vol, dry-basis	6.08	6.68	6.49
Flue gas temperature at cooler inlet (6)	°C	479	465	510.7
CO ₂ cooler thermal power (T _{out} = 400°C)	kW	64.4	50.6	85.49

3.2 1D model

The 1D model utilized 0D model results for streams 2, 3, 4, and 7 as its inputs, as well as the obtained diameter for the reactor. With these inputs, the 1D model was used to evaluate how heterogeneous reactions between the raw meal and gas occur with respect to the reactor height. The objective is to find a suitable height of the reactor to obtain the desired calcination degree for the material.

The following figures (Figures 6-8) present 1D profiles of gas composition and velocity, temperature, and the calcination degree as a function of riser height for different fuels to find the height that exceeds 90% calcination degree.

Figure 6. 1D model results for biogas.

Figure 7. 1D model results for biochar.

Figure 8. 1D model results for SRF and biochar.

The calcination occurs mostly at the bottom of the reactor where the temperature is high, and materials are fresh. The reaction rate decays as the temperature decreases as well as the calcination degree increases. The placement of assumed leakage airs can be seen as stepwise decreases in CO₂ concentration and corresponding increases in N₂ and O₂ concentration every 6 meters. From the 1D model results it is observed that the calcination degree exceeds 90% at approximately 30 m height for the reactor bottom with every fuel modeled. Therefore, this can be considered as the minimum height of the reactor for the investigated preliminary design.

3.3 3D model

For the 3D study, the case with SRF and biochar was chosen. The boundary conditions have been listed in Chapters 2.5 and 3.1. The shape of the bottom geometry and the locations of the different inlets were illustrated earlier in Figure 5. The height of the reactor tube above the mixing chamber was selected as 30 m.

Figure 9 presents the gas composition after the calciner modeled by the different models. The model results are well aligned although the model approaches are quite different from each other.

Figure 9. Comparison of modeled gas compositions after the calciner.

Figure 10a presents the modeled calcination degree of the material exiting the calciner compared with the outlet temperature. The differences between the models are relatively small. Figure 10b presents the cross-sectionally averaged CO₂ and calcination rate profiles in the 3D model. Based on the results, the 30 m tall calciner is sufficient to reach a good calcination degree and further extension of the height would yield marginal gains. A significant portion of the calcination occurs inside the mixing chamber, below the calciner reactor tube. This is expected given the higher concentration of fresh raw meal and the high temperatures in that region.

Figure 10. a) Modeled calcination degree and outlet temperature. b) Cross-sectionally averaged CO₂ share and calcination rate.

Figure 11 visualizes the 3D model results of carbon dioxide and calcination rate plotted at the surface of the model geometry. As seen in Figure 11a and b, the profiles along the reactor tube are well presented by one-dimensional profiles and the three-dimensional mixing phenomena mostly occur at the bottom of the calciner (Figure 11b), inside the mixing chamber. This is expected as the reactor is operating in pneumatic conveying with limited lateral movement of material.

Figure 11. 3D model results of a) and b) carbon dioxide and c) calcination rate.

Figure 12 presents the results at the middle cross-section across the model. Most of the oxygen (Figure 12a) for the combustion reactions enters with the main gas stream through the throat, while some of the recycled CO₂-rich gas and oxygen has been directed to the fuel and raw meal inlets. Most of the combustion heat comes from the combustion of the devolatilized gaseous species: the combustion profile is visualized by the combustion rate of ethene (Figure 12b). The combustion rate is highest in the locations, where the combustible material encounters oxygen. A smaller local combustion zone is located just after the fuel inlet. The oxygen entering through the fuel and raw meal inlets is quickly consumed and the primary combustion reactions occur just above the throat. This generates a high-temperature zone (Figure 12c) in this area with maximum temperatures reaching 1400°C.

Figure 12. Modeled fields at the middle cross-section of the model: a) oxygen, b) combustion rate of C₂H₄, and c) temperature.

Figure 13 presents the main calcium reactions at the bottom of the calciner: calcination (a), sulfation (b), and formation of belite (c). The calcination reaction is locally high inside the mixing chamber and it is effectively cooling this section. The SO_2 , which originates from the combustion reactions, is quickly captured by the CaO . It should be noted that the sulfation is inhibited in low-oxygen zones. Formation of belite requires high temperature, thus, it can be observed only at the bottom of the mixing chamber.

Figure 13. Calcium reactions at the middle cross-section of the model: a) calcination, b) sulfation, and c) formation of belite.

3.4 CFD model

The goal of the CFD simulations for the bottom part of the oxy-calcliner is to see if a suitable homogeneous distribution of particles can be achieved with the initially considered particle feeding arrangement, as lateral mixing is likely very limited during the pneumatic conveying higher in the reactor. Additionally, the CFD model should produce comparable process parameter results to the 3D model.

Figure 14 illustrates the velocity field of the gas phase in the initial calculation without particles (a) and in the final calculation, where the particles and reactions have been considered (b). There is a high-velocity gas jet at the bottom where the majority of the gas is injected into the mixing chamber through a throat. In the absence of particle flows and reactions, the gas flow within the mixing chamber stabilizes into a well-defined dual vortex. When the particle flows and gas sources from reactions are introduced, this stable vortex structure is disrupted, resulting in increased turbulence and transient flow behavior. This affects the flow profile at the bottom of the calciner reactor tube as well, where local and transient higher velocity zones can be detected as shown in Figure 14b. On average, the gas velocity inside the reactor tube is around 17 m/s, as desired.

Figure 14. a) Gas velocity vectors colored by velocity magnitude, calculation without particles. b) Gas velocity vectors colored by velocity magnitude, calculation with particles. The images present snapshots of instantaneous results in a transient simulation.

The fuel in the simulation was a mixture of SRF and biochar. The modeled fuel reactions encompassed moisture evaporation, devolatilization, and char combustion. According to the proximate analysis, a majority of the fuel consists of volatile material; therefore, the bulk of the heat generated during combustion arises from the combustion of devolatilized gaseous species. The actual gaseous products from devolatilization comprise a variety of hydrocarbons, hydrogen, carbon monoxide, and carbon dioxide. Due to computational constraints in the CFD simulation, this complexity was simplified; devolatilized gas was represented as ethene (C_2H_4), and the heating value for char combustion was adjusted to ensure that the overall heat generation matched the lower heating value of the fuel mixture.

Figure 15 presents snapshots of the mole fraction (a) and combustion rate (b) of ethene at the middle cross-section of the model. The devolatilization occurs rapidly inside the hot mixing chamber, leading to some immediate ethene combustion near the point of entry. Nevertheless, due to oxygen limitations, the bulk of the combustion occurs above the main gas inlet jet, where the fuel mixes with the oxygen from the inlet gas. The limited mixing rate of the gaseous species causes the combustion front to shift higher inside the mixing chamber and all the way up to the reactor tube. Some of the fuel particles circulate inside the mixing chamber, resulting in local combustion zones below the raw meal inlets, where supplemental oxygen is available.

Figure 15. a) Snapshot of instantaneous mole fraction of ethene. b) Snapshot of instantaneous reaction rate of ethene combustion ($kmol/m^3s$).

The oxygen field is depicted in Figure 16 as the mole fraction of oxygen at the middle cross-section (a) and the isosurface of 35% oxygen concentration colored by the combustion rate of ethene (b). The majority of the oxygen originates from the main gas inlet with some additional sources from the solid inlets. At the sides of the mixing chamber, the oxygen from the solid inlets is rapidly consumed by the combustion reactions. Figure 16b shows how oxygen from the main inlet is distributed inside the mixing chamber and toward the reactor tube. At this specific snapshot in time, the oxygen plume is oriented towards the front and right; however, this is an instantaneous condition and both the flow profile and the shape of the oxygen field are subject to continuous change.

Figure 16. a) Snapshot of instantaneous mole fraction of oxygen at the middle cross-section. b) Isosurface of the oxygen concentration at 35% colored by reaction rate of ethene combustion.

Figure 17 displays the gas (a) and particle (b) temperatures with a snapshot at the end of the simulation when the exit temperature has approximately stabilized. The temperature at the bottom of the mixing chamber is lower due, owing to the influence of cold inlet streams and the evaporation of the fuel moisture. Higher up in the mixing chamber the temperature increases due to combustion reactions, but this is tempered by endothermic calcination reactions. Within the reactor tube, the temperature is higher on the right side of the tube, which is consistent with the earlier shown combustion profile at this specific time snapshot. The hot fuel (and ash) particles circulate inside the mixing chamber serving to preheat the incoming fuel and raw meal particles. It should be noted that this simulation did not account for radiative heat exchange, which would likely decrease the temperature gradients and high local temperatures.

Figure 17. a) Snapshot of instantaneous gas temperature field at the middle cross-section [°C]. b) Particles colored by their temperature [°C]. The local maximum gas temperature was 1480°C and the local maximum particle temperature was 1800°C.

Figure 18a displays the calcination rate, while Figure 18b shows the carbon dioxide concentration at the middle section of the model at the end of the simulation. The calcination rate is discrete due to the discrete distribution of particles in the model. In the applied Dense Discrete Phase Model, particles are represented as parcels comprising multiple particles to decrease the computational cost and facilitate reasonable calculation times. The relatively sparse distribution of parcels leads to localized calcination zones. This creates localized gas sources, which are likely to disrupt the gas flow field and cause the observed rather chaotic flow profile. In an actual calciner, particle and gas-source distributions are more uniform. Therefore, the simulation results likely represent a 'worst-case' scenario, whereas the real-world process would probably operate more smoothly. Nonetheless, even this simulated calciner appears to function effectively, generating a carbon dioxide-rich gas stream, as illustrated in Figure 18b.

Figure 18. a) Snapshot of instantaneous calcination rate ($\text{kg/m}^3\text{s}$), logarithmic scale b) Snapshot of instantaneous mole fraction of carbon dioxide.

Regarding the limitations of the model capabilities, the CFD results are in good agreement with the 3D process model and indicate that the preliminary mixing chamber design of the oxy-calciner is performing as intended and can produce suitable temperature, gas velocity, and particle distribution profiles for the reactor tube to enable the high calcination performance in oxy-combustion conditions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Various levels of modeling tools were applied in studying the performance of the preliminary design of an oxy-fuel pre-calciner considered for integration into a cement plant to enable carbon capture and storage. All the different model results indicate the suitability of the preliminary design for well-performing, high calcination degree pre-calciner with oxy-combustion at around 50%-vol. oxygen concentration. The presented models were found to be in good agreement with each other and well-suited for further investigation of the process and further designs of this reactor concept. These models will be utilized in the project as the design is refined from the preliminary stage to the proposed version for construction.

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